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Evaluation & Impact Assessment
**DIAGNOSTIC CHECKLIST
FOR INTERACTIONS**

<p>MAA Scenario</p> <p>ENGAGING & INCENTIVISING INTERROGATING CREATING ADDRESSING APPLYING</p>	
<p>When to Implement</p>	<p>Used at the beginning of interactive innovation, and iteratively throughout the project.</p>
<p>Group Size</p>	<p>Any size</p>
<p>Level of Technical Difficulty</p>	<p>Chart interpretation - some technical expertise is required.</p>
<p>Time Needed</p>	<p>40 minutes approx.</p>
<p>Resources Required</p>	<p>Access to a computer, tablet or phone that has MS Office package installed.</p>
<p>Clustering with Other Tools</p>	<p>Tools # 5, 3.</p>

PURPOSE, BACKGROUND & LOGIC

Image source: [Roman Synkevych on Unsplash](#)

Purpose

The tool is useful to perform an analysis of the state of the different interactions in each stage of the initiative. Through this, the user can determine which aspects of their process should be improved and which, on the contrary, fit with an established standard. This self-evaluation process allows the manager to focus efforts and resources in areas that have a deficit, thus improving the results. Likewise, it offers the possibility of identifying the level of interaction with the support innovation system and whether it is sufficient or not.

The checklist is commonly used for self-evaluation in project management, which is developed by establishing the fundamental criteria under which it will be evaluated.

Background and Logic

In an interactive innovation initiative, a central theme is an adequate interaction with the actors. Interaction can be understood as an exchange of knowledge, information, or opinions between two or more actors, which can be institutions, NGOs, universities, etc. The interactions can be subdivided into typologies, namely:

- Interaction with financing mechanisms: all those actors that can finance or sponsor an initiative idea, with whom a strong and constant relationship is required for a correct exchange of information.
- Interactions within the initiative: the members of the initiative or the actors that are constantly associated with it throughout the entire innovation process, maintaining a formal link between them.
- Interaction with other actors that are not formally involved: Actors with whom there are constant connections throughout the initiative but who do not formally belong to its central nucleus. These actors are aware of the initiative and exert influence on it, either positively or negatively, for example, collaborators, suppliers, etc.
- Interaction with the context: Aspects of the context, both formal (policies, laws, government) and informal (culture, society, norms), that inadvertently affect the initiative and that generally require a monitoring process (competitors).
- Interaction with social challenges: Social challenges are common problems today. The initiatives that innovate interact with these challenges since in some way they contribute to their solution.

All these interactions are crucial for the success of the initiative, so they must be monitored throughout the, as well as considered during the planning and execution of the initiative. In this way, the user can determine which aspects of their process should be improved. If it is used periodically, it is also useful to monitor the changes.

This tool is designed for initiatives that want to determine the status of the innovation initiative interactions. The tool can be used by initiative coordinators to monitor the crucial aspects for the success of innovation and help decision-making. It can also be used for evaluators who want to quickly detect areas of possible improvement and areas of achievement, to focus their more detailed analysis. If they are new initiatives in a state of planning, this tool can be very useful in generating a guided reflection of users on relevant aspects of innovation and therefore contribute to planning. This tool can be used in conjunction with Tool #5 and 3, as good instruments to start planning initial actions.

Materials

- MS Excel file.

METHOD/HOW-TO GUIDE

This tool is a data visualization system that aims to guide the user's reflection on relevant topics for the correct development of the initiative. At the same time, allow simple visualization of results, facilitating interpretation and decision-making.

What do you need? How to prepare for it?

To use this tool, it is necessary to have access to a computer, tablet or phone that has the Office package installed. The Excel file is both the analysis matrix and the template for collecting information. Initial tabs are used to enter the information, while the following are created automatically, allowing the data to be viewed. If the data collection process wants to be done outside the Excel program, it is sufficient to print the first tabs of the Excel. However, to use the visualization system, data entry is required.

Excel Structure

When opening the Excel file, the user will find three tabs, the first of which is the "Checklist", where the data should be entered, and the other two dedicated to two different formats for the results.

Once positioned in the checklist tab, the user will find a matrix divided into four stages, each having four or five categories of interaction that are related to it. The table also has three columns, namely interactions, topics, and assessment.

The column 'Assessment' is the only one that the user can modify depending on their considerations. The results tabs "Graphic Results" and "Matrix Results" will be produced autonomously when the data entry process is finished. In addition, the Results Tabs can be printed for further interpretation if desired.

Data Entry

Once placed on the "Checklist" tab, the user will find a matrix divided into three columns. The first column 'Interaction' describes the interaction to which the statement is referred. The statement is detailed in the column 'Topics'. The user must reflect on them and then include in the column "Assessment" a number from 0 to 4 that corresponds to the option that best fits in each case, considering the criteria displayed on the upper side of the tab.

The input information necessary for the use of this tool can be obtained in several ways:

- The initiative manager autonomously;
- Through a meeting with the steering committee;
- Through a participatory workshop with the members of the team and the closest parties;
- Through stakeholder surveys, that is, submitting them to the same questions on the checklist, asking them how they think the initiative has developed in this area. Then average the results;
- The above tools can be integrated to average results;

However, it should be noted that the more participatory the gathering of the information, the more objective the result will be.

Diagnostic checklist for interactions

You need to fill the "Assessment" column considering the following criteria

0 It is not true at all
 1 It is not true with some exceptions
 2 It is true in most of the cases
 3 Yes, it is true almost always
 4 Yes, it is the norm

Pathway 1: Capturing, articulating and nurturing new ideas		
Interactions	Topics	Assessment
Interaction 1: Policy	I have access to relevant sources of information on the funders' priority objectives	4
	I have access to relevant sources of information on the requirements for funding	0
	I know the success factors to be selected	2
	I know projects that have been successful in obtaining financing	4
	I have identified the actors I need during each stage of my project	3
	I have enough contacts for each stage of the project	3
Interaction 2: Interactions within the interactive innovation case itself	The project has been realistic in the objectives that it was proposed	3
	The project has an adequate balance between the needs of the actors and those of the funders	3
	I know when to contact the actors I need	2
Interaction 3: Interaction with others: partners, stakeholders, etc.	We are generating enough space for the exchange of knowledge	2
	We are giving all team members the opportunity to give their opinion	0
	We are building common goals among all team members	1
	Our work team is capable of carrying out the idea in terms of resources and knowledge	2
Interaction 4: Interaction with other actors	I have identified actors that could help me with a product or service	3
	I have identified actors that can be a source of learning for my project	3

Checklist Graphic Results Matrix Results +

Illustration 1. Screenshots of the "Checklist" tab

EXPECTED RESULTS

Once the values have been inserted into the checklist, the user must go to the “Graphic results” and “Matrix results” tabs to see the results obtained.

If the results are not displayed automatically, it will be necessary to refresh the data (Select Data > Refresh All)

By completing the questionnaire, it will be possible to know at which stage and to which types of actors and interactions greater efforts should be assigned.

Graphic Results

There are two spider graphs, one that exemplifies the current situation of the initiative concerning the stages and interactions. It should be mentioned that the further from the centre of the figure the lines are, the better the result will be in terms of the stages of an initiative and/or type of interaction. This type of visualization allows an overview of the state of the interactions, regardless of the stage of the initiative, as well as the state of the interactions in general at each stage. To make more conscious decisions on specific aspects that are failing in the process, it will be necessary to proceed with the results matrix in the next tab.

Illustration 3. Screenshot of the tab ‘Graphic results’

Matrix Results

In this tab, a matrix is presented with each of the topics evaluated by the user in the checklist painted in different colours that indicate the performance of the initiative, depending on the value assigned to each item. This is so that a detailed or general visualization of all aspects can be made. The topics are arranged in a matrix format, where both interactions and stages are interrelated. For a more

in-depth analysis, the quality of the initiative's interaction can be visually determined by stage, analysing it vertically, or by the type of interaction, analysing it horizontally. In this visualization, the results are interpreted according to a colour code described in the legend. The aspects in red are those that have been evaluated negatively; therefore, if the context requires it, actions should be taken to improve each aspect.

Illustration 4. Screenshot of the tab 'Matrix results'

